

FUNCTIONING OF IMMUNE SYSTEM OF BABIES WITH CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS

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Actuality: In recent years, there has been an upward trend in the incidence of cardiovascular disease. For example, studies show an increase in frequency of 2 times in children under 14 years of age, and 2.5 times in adolescents. All this indicates an improvement in the results of diagnosing CVD diseases at this age. However, there is a late diagnosis of CHD, some of which are spontaneously detected only in adolescents. According to literature sources, the frequency of occurrence of the most common nosological forms of congenital heart disease in different age periods is diverse. All this testifies to the low detection rate of CHD in this group of children [1,4].

One of the main cells of adaptive immunity are T-lymphocytes. The

Purpose of the study: to study and evaluate the main indicators of cellular immunity in children with congenital heart defects in the dynamics of surgical correction.

Materials and methods: 142 sick children with CHD aged from 1 month to 18 years, hospitalized in the period from 2018-2021 in the Bukhara Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Hospital, to the Department of Pediatric Cardiology were involved in the clinical study. The exclusion criteria for the selection of patients were: endocrine and immunological diseases in parents, congenital heart disease with Down's syndrome. The control group consisted of 30 healthy children (16 boys and 14 girls).

Of the total number of those hospitalized with congenital heart disease, there were more boys - 73 (51.4±0.2%) than girls - 69 (48.6±0.3%). Of these, children with VSD were 45 (31.7%), ASD - 32 (22.5%), TOF - 33 (23.2%) and TGA - 32 (22.5%) children.

Conclusions: Based on the obtained and presented results of the study, it was found that surgical correction of CHD with partial or complete removal of the thymus contributes to the development of innate and adaptive immunity deficiency. The presence of CHD, especially blue ones, contributes to the development of tissue respiration disorders and the formation of immunological insufficiency, which in turn significantly worsens the condition of patients, reduces the effectiveness of conservative therapy for hemodynamic disorders. In

turn, this leads to a delay in the surgical treatment of CHD. Circulatory disorders, hypoxemia in CHD and cardiac surgery followed by thymectomy contribute to the development of immunodeficiency in children.

In this way, all established data proves the need not only for immunocorrection in the postoperative period, but also for improving the methods of surgical correction of CHD.

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